

GRAPHENE/NICKEL COMPOSITE NANOWIRES UNDER UNIAXIAL COMPRESSION: A MOLECULAR DYNAMICS SIMULATION STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Graphene is of great interest because of its excellent mechanical, electrical and thermal properties, which make it possibly to be an ideal reinforcement for nanocomposites. Using molecular dynamics simulations, here we focused on the compressive behaviours of the nanolayered graphene/nickel composite nanowires (NWs) at different temperature, with considering layer spacing effect. A comparative study was conducted on the compressive mechanical properties of single-crystalline nickel NWs and graphene/nickel composite NWs. The simulation results show that the composites NWs exhibit higher peak yield stress. The analysis on deformation shows that graphene can serve as an impermeable interface, blocking the motion of dislocation and leading the dislocations piled up, which increase the ultimate strength of composites NWs without compromising of ductility. The plastic deformation is mainly limited in the single layer of metal, which consistent with the experiment observation. In addition, the smaller the layer spacing of nanolayered composites is, the higher the ultimate yield strength of the composites NWs could be. The present results are expected to contribute to the design of the metal nanocomposites enhanced by graphene.

1 INTRODUCTION

Graphene exhibits excellent mechanical, electrical and thermal properties [1-6], which attracts great attention and intensive study in applied physics and material science. In particular, graphene is specified by both superior tensile strength of 130 GPa and Young modulus of 1 TPa [7], and the extreme surface-to-volume ration makes it possibly to be an ideal reinforcement for nanocomposites. Over the past decade, many research groups have successfully synthesized graphene-based nanocomposites with polymer-, ceramic- and metal-matrix, which exhibits superior mechanical properties and show great potential applications in nanoscale devices [8-11]. In particular, in recent years, due to widely using of metal-matrix composites, the fabricated process has made great progress. The mechanical properties of graphene get more full utilization in metal-matrix nanocomposites. Such nanocomposites reinforced by graphene exhibit enhanced mechanical characteristics, as compared to pure metal material.

Kim et al. [12] recently fabricated Cu- and Ni- matrices nanolayered composites reinforced by only single or double atomic layers of graphene via chemical vapor deposition method, showing superior compressive mechanical properties. Different from other randomly distributed graphene composite, graphene are first time to distribute flatly and equal layer spacing at axial direction of the metal nanopillar. The ultra-high strengths of 1.5 and 4.0 GPa for copper-graphene with 70nm repeat layer

spacing and nickel-graphene with 100 nm repeat layer spacing, respectively. These values are significantly higher than ever reported, even more about 52% than the theoretical strength in case of Ni [12]. They noted that the graphene blocked dislocation propagation across the metal-graphene interface through experiments. In addition, they experimentally revealed that the flow stress increases with diminishing the metal layer thickness [12], the results are similar to previous reports on metal nanolayered composites [13, 14]. Chang et al. [15] studied full atomistic simulations on nanoindentation of nickel-graphene nanocomposites with varied numbers of layers of graphene sheets. The results showed that as the number of layers of graphene sheets increases, the hardness of the nanocomposites decreases, but the maximum elastic deformation of nickel-graphene nanocomposites increases. Ovid'ko et al. [16] theoretically studied that competition between plastic deformation and fracture processes in metal-graphene layered composites. They found the strength of metal-graphene layered composites as functions of the key structural parameters, including the metallic layer thickness λ and graphene layer thickness h .

As far as we know, there have been only a few attempts to investigate the mechanical behaviours of graphene/metal nanocomposites, and the limited studies mainly focused on the synthesis and experiments. Especially, for the nickel-graphene nanolayered composites, a fundamental understanding of deformation mechanism under mechanical loading is lacking, which is a prerequisite for application of this novel nanocomposites.

In this work, the emphasis is focused on the compressive behaviours of the nanolayered graphene/nickel composite NWs using the molecular dynamics (MD) simulations, which has been proved to be a powerful method to simulate the mechanics of nanomaterials [17, 18]. Furthermore, we discuss the effects of spacing between graphene layers and temperature on the strength. Our findings could be helpful to further understand strengthening mechanisms of graphene/nickel nanolayered composites.

2 MODEL AND METHOD

Based the experiments [12], the configuration of the graphene/nickel NWs is built as shown in Fig. 1, in which four layers of red atoms for graphene sheets are uniformly embedded into nickel [111] NWs, since the (111) planes are the energetically favourable planes for plastic deformation in face centered cubic (FCC) nickel [15], and periodic boundary condition is applied along this direction. Other two free surfaces are (1 -1 0) and (1 1 -2). The lateral dimension a of the NW is about 8 nm, and the repeat spacing of graphene sheets d varies from 1.2 nm to 12 nm.

All the MD simulation in this paper are performed with using the large-scale atomic molecular massively parallel simulator (LAMMPS) [19], with combination of embedded atom method (EAM) [20] potential, reactive empirical bonding order (REBO) [21] potential and Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential together, which has been proved to be able to depict the two-type-atom system well [15]. The potential of LJ which describe the van der Waal's interaction can be given by the equation

$$U_{ij} = 4\varepsilon_{ij} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] \quad (1)$$

Where U_{ij} is a pair potential energy between the atom i and j . ε_{ij} and σ_{ij} are the coefficient of well-depth energy and equilibrium distance, respectively. Here $\varepsilon_{\text{Ni-C}} = 0.023049$ eV and $\sigma_{\text{Ni-C}} = 2.852$ Å [22] are adopted for all simulations.

Before loading, the simulation cells are first relaxed using the conjugate gradient method and then equilibrated at specified temperature (10 K and 300 K) using the Nose-Hoover thermostat [23] for 500 ps with NPT ensemble, in order to achieve stress free state in the axial direction. In applying strain, the axial dimension is decreased at a constant rate of $10^8/s$ at NVT ensemble, namely [111] orientation. The equations of motion are integrated using the Verlet leapfrog method [24] with a time step of 1 fs. The stress component is calculated using the Virial theorem [25]. The snapshots of the MD results are processed by the package of ATOMEYE [26].

Many researcher has studied the properties of different single-crystalline metal NWs, including nickel. Here, in order to compare the mechanical properties of single-crystalline metal NWs and composites NWs, we do some comparison simulation between the two types of NWs at the same initial conditions.

Figure 1: Illustration of the graphene/nickel nanolayered nanowires models. (a) Schematic of crystallographic orientations and transverse directions of graphene/nickel nanocomposites, red lines represent graphene. (b) Atomistic model at initial stage colored by their coordination numbers.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical properties of graphene/nickel NWs

This study address compressive tests of graphene/nickel layered [111] NWs. Stress-strain relationships are obtained to locate the initial yield point and to determine the size effect on yield stress. The snapshots of the compressive deformation are captured to understand the yield mechanisms of the NWs under uniaxial compressive loading. In order to examine the details in its interior structure, deformations of the NWs shape and inside defects evolution are snapped from different perspectives.

Fig. 2a shows the comparison results between single-crystalline nickel and graphene/nickel composites NWs at the spacing distance of about 6.0 nm at a temperature of 10 K. According to the composites NWs, graphene served as a reinforcement inclusion enhanced the mechanical properties. However, the compressive modulus has no obvious change due to the addition of graphene under compressive loading. The reason is that the elastic modulus of graphen at out-of-plane direction is less than that of in-plane.

The compressive stress-strain response for graphene/nickel NWs at the temperature of 10 K is shown in Fig. 2b. This figure shows that the deformation of graphene/nickel composite NWs under uniaxial compression, which can be characterized with three dominant regimes: elastic, strain-hardening and strain-softening regimes. It is interesting to notice that the elastic regime can be divided into two stages, as marked by the red line 1 and red line 2. There are four configurations with different stacking orders for the interfacial structure of graphene-ni, namely, top-fcc, top-hcp, hcp-fcc and top-bridge [27]. As load increases, the carbon atoms can be embedded into the metal lattices. So the apparent modulus of elasticity of this nanocomposite is obtained by the calculation of the slope of line 2, the value is 400 GPa at temperature of 10 K, which is obviously larger than 300 GPa of line 1.

Figure 2: Compressive stress-strain curves for graphene/nickel composites NWs at layer spacing of 6.0 nm at 10 K. (a) Compare between nickel NWs and graphene/nickel NWs. (b) Red line 1 and line 2 indicate the two different elastic moduli in elastic regime.

As the compression load is applied at a fixed strain rate, the compressive curve of graphene/nickel NWs shows transient drop, like point A, point B and point C, before arrive the peak point of D in Fig. 2b. Point A to point D can be considered as the strain-hardening stage for graphene/nickel nanocomposites. The initial yield stress of 17 GPa is much lower than the maximum yield stress of 25.2 GPa. And the ultimate yield strain is about 7%. Compared to the single crystal nickel, the ultimate stress is 20.3 GPa and the failure strain is about 5.6%, which proved that graphene inclusion can enhanced the mechanical properties without sacrificing of toughness.

To better understand the plastic mechanisms, the microstructure evolution during compression was carefully analyzed, as shown in Fig. 3, which presents the point A in Fig. 2b. From the snapshots of atom evolution, we can find that the dislocation with Burgers vector of $\vec{b} = [101]/2$ slip in the $\{111\}$ slip plane, which is different from the tensile loading that the nucleation and propagation of Shockley partial dislocation with Burgers vector ($\vec{b} = [112]/6$) in the same slip system [17]. We found that the onset of plasticity corresponds to the emission of $\{111\}\langle 112\rangle$ leading partial dislocations near the interface of graphene from the sharp edges where the atoms have the higher energy [18, 28], as shown in Fig. 3b. Then, the trailing partial dislocation with the nucleation from same site (Fig. 3d), following the leading partial dislocation, and combine to form a unit dislocation propagating in the $\{111\}$ slip plane. The dislocation process can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{6}[2\bar{1}1] + \frac{1}{6}[112] \rightarrow \frac{1}{2}[101] \quad (2)$$

For the graphene-free NWs, simulation results show that dislocation glide can across the whole wire and incorporate in the opposite site of the side surfaces and no dislocation are left in the wire, resulting that the sudden drop of stress-strain curve, which agrees well with the previous literatures reported [17, 28]. However, the interesting thing happened in graphene/nickel NWs, as shown in Fig. 3, the leading partial dislocation moving along the slip surface is eventually pinned near the interface but never penetrates beyond the single layer of graphene due to the strong C-C bond network of the graphene. This observation is consistent with the pile-up of dislocations at the graphene interface observed in Kim's experiments [12].

Figure 3: Snapshots of graphene/nickel composites nanowires at the layer spacing of 6.0 nm ($T=10$ K) under compressive loading ($\varepsilon = 4.7\%$, $\sigma = 17$ GPa). Dislocation nucleation from the surface and propagation in a slip plane is observed at one metal layer between two graphene layers. (a) The dislocation nucleates from the corner. (b) The leading partial dislocation emission. (c) The leading partial dislocation slips along the slip plane. (d) The trailing partial dislocation coming out from the same corner and combining with the leading one to form a unit dislocation. (e) The full dislocation slips in the nanowires. (f) The dislocation block by graphene. For clarity, the front surface and perfect fcc atoms are not shown. Atoms are colored according to CNA. The following snapshots of the MD simulations are processed with the same method.

Figure 4: Snapshots of graphene/nickel nanowires at the layer spacing of 6.0 nm ($T=10$ K) under compressive loading ($\varepsilon = 7\%$, $\sigma = 25.2$ GPa). Dislocations piles up from (a) to (f) in a metal layer.

With the load increasing, new partial dislocations nucleate in this metal layer, but the previous pinned dislocations never propagate across the interface. At the strain arrived about 7%, the

nanocomposites reached the maximum stress, as shown in Fig. 4, and more dislocations appear and interact with each other with no dislocation penetrating the interface.

The stress-strain curve of graphene/nickel composite NWs and single crystal nickel NWs under compressive loading at the temperature of 300 K is shown in Fig. 5. Similarly, it is obvious to observe that graphene served as a reinforcement inclusion enhanced the mechanical properties at 300 K. Moreover, strain-hardening can be observed at strain of 5.2% for graphene/nickel composites NWs. Combination of the snapshot of defect evolution in Fig. 6a, we can find that a full dislocation slip in the $\{111\}$ slip plane for graphene/nickel NWs at 300 K. Then, a large number of dislocations launched at another metal layer at strain of 5.8% (Fig. 6b - Fig. 6c), causing the stress-strain line drop. Fig. 6d shows the plastic deformation of whole graphene/nickel NWs at strain of 8%. The plastic deformation mainly limited at one metal layer, which can be attributed to dislocation blocking by graphene and a large number of dislocation pile-up.

Figure 5: Compressive stress-strain curves for graphene/nickel NWs at layer spacing of 6.0 nm at 300k.

Figure 6: Snapshots of graphene/nickel nanowires at the layer spacing of 6.0 nm ($T=300$ K) under compressive loading.

3.2 Size effect for graphene/nickel NWs

For many metallic multilayered composites, layer thickness is also an important tunable parameter to get better mechanical properties. Fig. 7 shows the ultimate stress of this graphene/nickel nanolayered NWs change with the repeat layer spacing from 1.2 nm to 12 nm at the temperature of 300 K. It is clearly showed that the strength increase quickly corresponding to a reduction of layer

spacing, which is in agreement with results in the simulations and experiments. The value of the maximum and minimum of ultimate stress is 28.7 GPa and 17.2 GPa, respectively. In another word, the yield stress of the Ni NWs reinforced by the single atomic layered graphene enhanced with the increasing content of the inclusion. And the results show that the critical stress is well fitted by the conventional Hall-Petch relationship [29, 30], $\sigma \propto d^{1/2}$, which describes the yield stress of a polycrystalline solid as a function of its grain size. As shown in Fig. 7, the compressive yield stresses of graphene/nickel NWs tend to approach a constant value with increasing the repeated layer spacing. Because the single crystal of nickel NWs is an anisotropic materials.

Figure 7: The yield stress of graphene/nickel NWs as a function of layered spacing d .

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we study the compressive properties of the nanolayered graphene/nickel composite NWs by using molecular dynamics simulations, taking into account the size effects of layer spacing, and temperature. The results show that the ultimate loading of graphene/nickel NWs is evidently higher than the single crystal nickel NWs, at the same time without sacrifice toughness. In addition, the smaller the layer spacing of nanolayered composites is, the higher the ultimate yield strength of the composites NWs could be. The simulation results match well the predicted results by Hall-Petch model. Graphene is an effective barrier against dislocation motion, which increase the ultimate strength of composites NWs without compromising of ductility. The present results are expected to contribute to the design of the metal nanocomposite enhanced by graphene and to improve the mechanical properties of metals.

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